

**A STUDY ON GENDER INEQUALITIES AND EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN IN
ARIYALUR DISTRICT IN TAMIL NADU**

A.Saravanan

Ph.D., Scholar, PG & Research Department of Economics,
Gobi Arts & Science College, Gobichettipalayam-638453, Erode district, Tamil Nadu

Dr.A.Raja

Associate Professor, PG & Research Department of Economics,
Gobi Arts & Science College, Gobichettipalayam-638453, Erode district, Tamil Nadu

Abstract

The objectives of the study are to identify the socio-economic characteristics of women, to identify the extent of gender inequalities in terms of the selected socio-economic indicators and to identify the structural variables that impede women empowerment in Ariyalur district of Tamil Nadu. Ariyalur District forms the universe of the study. A list of households from 40 selected village was prepared, out of which 1705 samples were selected at random. The study was concluded that the level of Women Empowerment in the rural areas of Ariyalur districts is far from satisfactory. The study also highlights the fact that inspite of many Development Programmes initiated by the Government over years, the socio economic institutions that impede women empowerment still has considerable role in the slow progress of women empowerment in the areas. The rural women's access to income earning, access asset ownership, political participation, educational access, attending healthcare needs and exposure to family level decision making etc., are yet to be reached to the stake holders.

Keywords: Gender, Inequality, Women, Empowerment

1. INTRODUCTION

Gender is one of the universal dimension on which the status difference of men and women are based. It is a social contract indicating the socially and culturally prejudiced roles that men and women are to follow. The issue of gender inequality on the other hand, has been noticed to be a universal feature in almost all developing societies of the world. Unlike women in developed countries who are in relative terms economically empowered and have a powerful say on decision making, women in developing countries are reported to be passive, silent, and their voice has been stifled by many economic and cultural factors. Revelations from many empirical studies showed that low decision making power among women in developing countries is more pronounced at household level. About 50 percent of the women in a western Indian state do not feel even to take a sick child (Visaria, 1993 cited in Desai et-al, 2005) to a doctor without the

approval of their husband and 70 percent of the women do not make decisions regarding the purchase of their own or their children's clothing. Though, the number of women in national parliaments across the world has been found increasing, no country in the world has yet achieved gender parity in their participation in decision making at national level. The percentage of parliamentary seats held by women in 2005 was 16 percent at world level, 21 percent in developed countries and 14 percent in developing countries, which might be largely attributed to the type of electoral system that prevails in these countries, women's socio-economic status, socio-cultural traditions and beliefs in the family and society as well as the women's double burden of work and family responsibilities (UNFPA). Moreover, different studies on gender related issues across the world also indicated the fact that lack of access to productive resources viz., land, education, employment opportunities, basic health, protection of basic human rights, low decision making power, subject to violence and harmful traditional practices are some of the reasons leading to the socio-economic marginalization of women. The gender gap between men and women in these indicators has negative impact on the overall development of the country in general and on the demographic and health outcomes of individuals in particular. Besides, gender differences in power roles and rights affect health, fertility control, survival and nutrition through women's access to health care, lower control over their bodies and sexuality and restriction in material and non-material resources.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dunn D (1993) has found that relative to men, women in these groups have far more limited access to both educational and employment resources. The study also suggested that socioeconomic development serves to reduce the disadvantage of scheduled caste group women relative to men. Among the scheduled groups considered to be more developed the observation was that the standard empowerment indicators viz., education and employment has less inequality.

Tandley Omprakash Sridevi (2005) has concluded that the level of economic equality and independence are the real indicators for measuring the status of

women in any society. Moreover, a complex and stratified society, the status of women generally differs from time to time, region to region, class to class, religion to religion and from occupation to occupation the study added. The study also was under observation that there should be proper and appropriate interrelation strategies which would be a big source of assistance to empower women. It is not enough that the women are made independent but they must also change their self-perception at large.

3. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study are to identify the socio-economic characteristics of women, to identify the extent of gender inequalities in terms of the selected socio-economic indicators and to identify the structural variables that impedes women empowerment in Ariyalur district of Tamil Nadu

4. METHODOLOGY

Ariyalur District forms the universe of the study. A list of households from 40 selected village was prepared, out of which 1705 samples were selected at random. All the women respondents selected for the study were married, found in the age group of 22-70 years. In order to make comparison with men with respect to the gender related and empowerment characters an equal number of men respondents from the same households were interviewed on the basis of a specifically designed schedule. Thus, the present study is confined to a total sample of 1705 respondents of each male and female category of the same sampling units, selected from 40 villages of Ariyalur district in Tamil Nadu.

For the objective evaluation of data relating to the various socio-economic characteristics of the study, statistical tools starting from simple tabular and percentage analysis to the multiple regression analyses were employed in the study. A conventional statistical analyses viz., Mean, Median, Standard Deviation, Maximum and Minimum values of the variables were performed to identify the mean statistics of the variables are also included in the study.

Gender gap pertaining to the district and taluk level data were worked as a measure of gender disparity based on the absolute difference between the value of the female scores over male scores in each category of the sample respondents as detailed below;

$$\text{Gender Gap } (g) = \text{Percentage of Female} - \text{Percentage of Males}$$

Gender gap index for each category of data were worked out as the ratio between the absolute female and male scores as the following type;

$$\text{Gender Gap Index} = \frac{X_f}{X_m} - 1$$

Where X_f / X_m is a gender ratio which shows that the Gender gap index is the absolute difference between the gender ratio and 1.

Women Empowerment Index

The Women Empowerment Index for each dimension viz., [Personal Autonomy index (PAUI), Economic Decision Making Index (EDMI), Households Decision Making Index (HDMI) and Political Autonomy Index (POAI)] were constructed by using United National Development Programme (UNDP, 2005) formulation on Human Development Index;

$$I_j = \frac{X_{ij} - \text{Min}(X_i)}{\text{Max}(X_i) - \text{Min}(X_i)}$$

Where,

I_j = Dimension Index

X_{ij} = Actual score value

$\text{Min}(X_i)$ = Minimum score value

$\text{Max}(X_i)$ = Maximum score value

For each of these four dimensions, an Equally Distributed Equivalent Percentage (EDEP) was calculated, as a population – weighted average, by using the following formula;

$$\text{EDEP} = \left[\frac{\text{Female population shares}}{\text{Female Index}} + \frac{\text{Male population shares}}{\text{Male Index}} \right]^{-1}$$

For political and economic participation and decision-making, the Equally Distributed Equivalent Percentage (EDEP) is then indexed by dividing it by 50. The rationale for this indexation is that in an ideal society, with equal empowerment of sexes, the GEM variables would equal 50%, that is, women's share would equal men's share for each variable. Finally, the Cumulative Women Empowerment Index (CWEI) is calculated as a simple average of the four dimensions indexed EDEPs.

$$CWEI = \frac{PAUI + EDM I + HDEI + POAI}{4}$$

Where,

CWEI = Cumulative Women Empowerment Index

PAUI = Personal Autonomy Index

EDMI = Economic Decision Making Index

HDMI = Households Decision Making Index

POAI = Political Autonomy Index

It is hypothesised that all the indices constructed above have positive relationship with Composite Women Empowerment Index, which is the composite index of the four separate indices. Besides, there are some explanatory variables viz., family type, family size, age, cultural belief, fear of violence, distances of healthcare centres from respondents home, distance of school from respondents home, which are also hypothesised to have negative relationship with the combined Women Empowerment Index.

Determinants of Women Empowerment

In order to estimate the determinants of women empowerment in the sample district, both qualitative (logistic regression) and quantitative (multiple regression) methods of analysis were employed.

Qualitative analysis was performed by using logistic model or logistic regression model is an attempt to model the probability of a **yes / success** outcomes using the linear function of the predictors. In other words, logistic regression is one type of discrete choice model which in general predict categorical dependent variables either binary or multiple.

It may be recalled that the logistic method of estimation is based on logistic curve for all values of the regressors, the value of dependent variables falls between 0 and 1. The probability function is a non-linear function and follows a logistic curve. This is a more realistic pattern of change in the probability compared to other qualitative dependent variable models like the Probit on the ground that the odds ratio which is a measure of the strength and deviation of relationship between the two variables and has a special property as not requiring variables to be normally distributed and 2) a mathematical transformation of the odds ratio is the logit model, and this mathematical transformation removes the problem of asymmetry existing in the odds ratio and intern make this method superior over other method.

The logistic regression model of incorporating the dependent variable women to be empowered (P_i) is of the following form;

$$P_i = P_i(Y_i = 1) = E(Y_i / X_i) = 1 / (1 + e^{\beta_1 + \beta_2 X_1})$$

Where, if $Y_i=1$, women are empowered and if $Y_i=0$, then the women are not empowered, $E(Y_i/X_i)$ is the expectation that a women is empowered given the value of exogenous variables (X_i), where betas are the parameters to be estimated. Similarly, the probability that the women are not empowered ($1-P_i$) can be estimate as;

$$L_i = \log(P_i / 1 - P_i) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_1 + u_i$$

Where, u_i follows the normal distribution with zero mean and variance equal to $1/[N_i P_i (1 - P_i)]$. The exogenous variables are in X_i and N_i denotes the number of respondents and natural logarithmic values were taken both dependent and exogenous variables for estimation.

Since, the purpose of the present analysis is to explore the magnitude of gender gap / empowerment of women in rural areas under the existing social structure in the district, a quantities multiple regression analyses was also performed. Although, there are various econometric techniques and lot of computational facilities are available for empirical analyses, the regression equations using the OLS method of the following type is the commonly used technique;

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \varepsilon$$

Where,

$Y = \text{Cumulative Women Empowerment Index (CWEI)}$

$\alpha = \text{Intercept}$

$X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n = \text{Independent variables}$

$\beta_1, \dots, \beta_n = \text{are the parameters to be estimated}$

$\varepsilon = \text{Random unobserved disturbance term, with the mean as zero and the variance as constant}$

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

The socio-economic characteristics of the selected sample households of Ariyalur district of Tamil Nadu is presented in table-1.

TABLE-I: SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SELECTED SAMPLE HOUSEHOLDS

Variables	N	%
No. of sample households	1705	
No. of Males	3491	
No. of Females	3717	
Total population	7208	
Family Type		
Nuclear	1477	86.63
Joint	228	13.37
Family size with		
Below 2 Members	116	6.80
2 - 4 Members	975	57.20
4 - 6 Members	519	30.40
Above 6 Members	95	5.60
Age Group distribution of respondents		
Below 30 Years	367	21.50
30 - 60 Years	1318	77.30
Above 60 Years	20	1.20

Educational Status of the respondents		
Illiterates	716	42.00
Literacy at Primary Level	419	24.60
Literacy at Secondary Level	411	24.10
Literacy at Higher Secondary and Above	159	9.30
Occupational Participation of respondents		
Farmers	170	9.97
Agricultural labourers	475	27.86
Industrial workers	88	5.16
Professionals	30	1.76
Self-Employed	26	1.52
Others	916	53.72
Income Distribution by Households		
Below Rs.25000	394	23.11
Rs.25000 - Rs. 50000	591	34.66
Rs.50000- Rs. 75000	279	16.36
Rs. 75000 - Rs. 100000	163	9.56
Above Rs. 100000	278	16.30
Asset distribution by Households		
Below Rs.2.5 lakhs	966	56.66
Rs.2.5 - Rs.5.0 lakhs	353	20.70
Rs.5.0 - Rs.7.5 lakhs	164	9.62
Rs.7.5 - Rs.10.0 lakhs	119	6.98
Above Rs.10.0 lakhs	103	6.04
Respondents access to media and communication net works	712	41.76
No. of households occupied political positions	16	0.94

Source: Survey Data

The socio-economic background of the sample women households selected for the study reveals that out of the 1705 sample household units selected for the study, the total of male population worked out for the entire sampling units in the district were 3491, while 3717 were females adding to the grand total population of 7208 which includes children below the age of 15 years. Out of the total sample units selected for the study, vast majority of the households were registered as nuclear type of families while only 13.37 percent of them were in the category of

joint family. The average family size of the sample households selected for the study was worked out to 4.23.

All sample households in the district, 6.80 percent of the households were with the family size of below 2 members, 57.20 percent were with 2-4 members, 30.40 percent were 4-6 members and 5.60 percent were with family size of above 6 members. The age group-wise distribution of the total sample households included in the study reveals that out of the total 1705 sample households selected for the study, little more than 77 percent of the respondents were in the age group of 30 – 60 years; while 21.50 percent were below the age of 30 years.

From the point of view of the educational status of the households selected for the study, 24.60 percent of the households had education at primary level; 24.10 percent and 9.30 percent had education at secondary and post secondary levels respectively. The occupational distribution of the sample households classified through post stratification showed that out of the 1705 sample household units selected for the study, highest percentage was recorded for agricultural labourers (49.56 percent) followed by farmers (24.46 percent).

Since percapita income is generally viewed to be an important indicator for measuring gender inequalities, out of the total sample households selected for the study, 23.11 percent of them were with the percapita income group of Rs.25000/- followed by 34.66 percent whose percapita income falls in the income group of Rs.25000-Rs.50000/-. On the other hand, more than 57 percent of the respondent households selected for the study were found in the income group of less than Rs.50000/- per annum, which might be due to the fact that women's participation in the earning activities in these areas are either be limited or viewed out of context in their societal belief.

The asset distribution of the households selected for the study indicated the fact that 56.66 percent of the household units selected for the study were with the asset group valued at less than Rs.2.5 lakhs, while 20.70 percent were recorded in the asset group worth of Rs.2.5 – 7.5 lakhs. Of the 1705 households selected for the study, only 6.04 percent of the households were with the asset group of Rs.10.0 lakh and above. On an average 41.76 percent of the women households selected for the study in the district have access to media and communication network, leaving the rest largely as unnoticed of from any communication and media networks.

The political participation of women households selected for the study also showed that in all, only 0.94 percent of the women households have occupied political positions.

5.2. GENDER INEQUALITIES IN SELECTED SOCIO-ECONOMIC INDICATORS

The gender gap estimates based on the primary data collected from Ariyalur district presented in table-2 showed that in the case of overall literacy, significant differences were observed in the gender ratio's between women and men in the district. The proportion of women literate in the district was 58.01 percent; it was 71.67 percent for men. The gender gap ratio for the overall literacy rate worked out in the district was 81 percent; indicating the fact that in the case of overall literacy, the district is witnessed with wider gender disparity in literacy rate.

TABLE-II: GENDER INEQUALITIES INDEXES FOR SELECTED INDICATORS

Indicators	Proportion of Women	Proportion of Men	Gender Gap	Gender Ratio	Deviation of Gender Ratio from 1	Absolute Deviation	Sub-Dimension	% contribution
Education Dimension								
Overall Literacy rate	58.01	71.67	-	0.81	-0.1907	0.1907		
Educational attainments at								
Primary Level	24.57	23.52	1.06	1.04	0.0449	0.0449	0.2274	14.99
Secondary Level	24.11	31.55	-7.45	0.76	-0.2361	0.2361		
Higher Secondary and above level	9.33	16.60	-7.27	0.56	-0.4382	0.4382		
Employment Dimension								
Labour Force Participation Rate	46.28	88.15	-	0.52	-0.4750	0.4750		
Proportion of farmer/agricultural labourers	37.83	58.77	-	0.64	-0.3563	0.3563	0.4528	29.84
Proportion of non-Agricultural labourers	5.16	10.91	-0.21	0.47	-0.5270	0.5270		
Women Empowerment Dimension								
Share in political participation	0.94	6.33	-5.40	0.15	-0.8519	0.8519		
Share in organized employment, Professionals and Self employment	3.28	18.48	-	0.18	-0.8225	0.8225	0.8372	55.17
Gender Gap Index							0.5058	100.00

A) Total of all absolute value of negative deviations : 3.8976

P-ISSN: 1544-8037

E-ISSN: 2378-9174

B) Total of all absolute value of positive deviations	:	0.0449
% contribution where female are worse off than male	:	98.8614
A) / (Value of total absolute deviations)	:	
% contribution where male are worse off than female	:	1.1386
B) / (Value of total absolute deviations)	:	

The sub-dimension index computed for education with the value of 0.2274, employment dimension index value of 0.4528 and women empowerment dimension index value of 0.8372, indicating the fact that women in the district are the most disadvantaged groups in the society. Thus to conclude the gender inequalities between women and men worked out for the Ariyalur District is shown widened in all dimensions viz., Education, Employment and Empowerment and the trend is not uniform among the three selected dimensions of the overall gender gap index.

5.3. THE DETERMINANTS OF WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

The study deals about the significant determinants of women empowerment in Ariyalur district of Tamil Nadu based on the primary data collected from 1705 respondents selected for this purpose. The logistic model was employed to analyse the determinants of women empowerment where the dependent variable is obtained from the respondents perception that whether they feel empowered or not. If the respondents perceive that she is empowered then the value is assigned to 1 and 0 if otherwise, thereby making the data on women empowerment (dependent variable) qualitative and estimated the impact of the factors that effects women empowerment in the district. Thus, the dependent variable in the Logit regression analysis is the dummy variable, and the various explanatory variables that affect the level of empowerment among women in the district and their relationship with women empowerment are; 1. Family type (FAMILY), 2. Family size (NOHM), 3. Age of the respondent (AGER), 4. Age difference between spouse (ADBS), 5. No. of children in a family (NOCF), 6. Education status (REDL), 7. Educational difference with spouse (EDWS), 8. Dependency ratio (DEPR), 9. Access to Assets (ASSET), 10. Access to media (MEDIA), 11. Access to Political participation (POLT), 12. Log

percapita income of the household (LOG-PINH). The estimated results of the regression coefficients using both the logistic and multiple regression models pertaining to the empowerment variables included are presented in table-3.

TABLE-III: ESTIMATED RESULTS OF THE EXPLANATORY VARIABLES INCLUDED IN THE LOGISTIC AND MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Explanatory variables	Empowerment Attributes of Qualitative Model		Empowerment Attributes of Quantitative Model		
	Coefficients	Sig.	Coefficients	t	Sig.
Constant	-3.186	.003	.189	4.830	.000
FAMILY	-.738	.000*	-.037	-3.541	.000*
NOHM	-.356	.000*	-.002	-.813	.416
AGER	.023	.002*	.001	2.632	.009*
ADBS	.038	.093**	-.008	-7.765	.000*
NOCF	.042	.549	-.001	-.438	.661
REDL	-1.072	.000*	.019	25.381	.000*
EDWS	.043	.006*	-.004	-4.940	.000*
DEPR	4.864	.000*	-.048	-2.907	.004*
ASSET	-.009	.943	.171	24.423	.000*
MEDIA	-.414	.001*	.023	3.777	.000*
POLT	-1.090	.000*	.100	15.243	.000*
LOG-PINH	.373	.000*	.002	.853	.394
R ²	.368		.523		
Chi-square	540.688	0.000			
Adjusted R ²			.520		
F			164.676		0.000*
N	1705		1705		

* Significant at 1 % level, ** Significant at 5 % level, *** Significant at 10 % level

The estimated regression co-efficients pertaining to the composite data presented in table-III indicated the fact that the fitted regression equation is statistically significant according to the (logit model) empowerment perception made in the study and explained 36 percent and 52 percent variation respectively in women empowerment which is due to the explanatory variables and depicts a moderate goodness of fit. The R² values of logistic multiple regression models. The Chi-Square and F values of the models are highly found significant and indicate that systematic variation in the empowerment variables are considerably larger. The positive signs registered for the explanatory variables namely age, education, access to ownership of assets, access to media

Volume III, Issue II, July – December 2010

and communication, access to political participation and log percapita income are those factors whose impact might make guidances and direct the policy makers and the institutions involved in the empowerment process, would enhance the women empowerment programmes across the country. The negative signs registered for the explanatory variables viz., family type, number of household members, age difference with spouse, educational difference with spouse, number of children in a family and dependency ratio have indicated for negative relationship with empowerment. The results obtained from the study therefore clearly depicts the fact that women empowerment in rural areas of the one selected for the study has some distinct requirements viz., age maturity, increasing the level of education, greater mobility to work force in paid work, ownership access to assets, access to media and communication net works, liberty to political participation and suitable avenues for employment to enhance the family income.

6. CONCLUSION

The study was concluded that the level of Women Empowerment in the rural areas of Ariyalur districts is far from satisfactory. The study also highlights the fact that inspite of many Development Programmes initiated by the Government over years, the socio economic institutions that impede women empowerment still has considerable role in the slow progress of women empowerment in the areas. The rural women's access to income earning, access asset ownership, political participation, educational access, attending healthcare needs and exposure to family level decision making etc., are yet to be reached to the stake holders. The status of rural women in these areas even today is treated secondary and no importance has been attached with them. Domestic violence, dowry harassments, female infanticide, wife beating, divorce and mental torture still continues which have a serious cumulative negative consequence on women's health and quality of life.

Therefore, to move forward with the objectives of the Women Empowerment and programmes initiatives which are operational in the country, the study recommends some concrete steps which are to be attended by all implementing agencies viz., Government Organisations, Non-Governmental Organisations, Women Developmental Organisations and all other stake holders and civil society to stimulate the process of women empowerment

effectively. Government intervention through legislation, planning and implementation must be stepped up to provide greater opportunity for the sustainable development of women at all levels, so that the discriminatory practices of women and the gender related issues against women would be addressed.

7. REFERENCES

1. UNDP, Measuring and Monitoring Gender Equality, Malaysia's Gender Gap Index, 2007
2. Dunn, D: "Gender Inequality in Education and Employment in the Scheduled Castes and Tribes of India", Population Research and Policy Review, Vol. 12 (1), 1993, pp. 53-70
3. Jamil Ahmad: "Gender Inequality and Women Empowerment: A Review", New Dimensions of Women Empowerment, Deep & Deep Publications Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi.
4. Tandley Omprakash Sridevi: "Empowerment of Women: A Systematic Analysis", Indian Development Foundation (IDF) Discussion Paper, 2005.
5. UNFPA: "Gender Inequality and Women Empowerment", Ethiopian Society of Population Studies, Addis Ahaha, October 2008.